

cultivar with excellent palatability and resistance to bacterial blight and blast.

NAU2159 was developed from a cross between Nanjing 11, a popular local variety, in Jiangsu Province, and IR29, a donor of disease resistance and waxy endperm.

In 4 yr demonstration (1985-88) along

the lower and middle reaches of the Yangtze River Valley, yields were 7-9 t/ha, 7.5 t/ha average. NAU2159 matures early (duration 130-135 d) and is adapted to the areas flanked by 29-34°N latitude, where a traditional rice - wheat cropping system prevails. Its

better performance results from the unique combination of traits inherited from both parents (see table).

It is acceptable to farmers in Henan, Anhui, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, and Guizhao Provinces, with more than 50,000 ha planted. □

Performance of some promising rice cultivars for tidal marshy swamps of Andamans

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We screened 330 cultivars during 1988 to identify a suitable rice variety for the low-lying marshy areas along the tidal creeks of Andamans. Cultures included

advanced bulk populations, elite lines, and F₁ anther culture derivatives from IRRI.

Seedlings (21-d-old) were transplanted in a field with normal soil and in a screening plot close to the sea (soil EC 6.5 dS/m and pH 4.2). The screening plot was allowed to be fully inundated by 50-60 cm seawater 7 d after transplanting. That water was maintained through the cropping period by bunding the experimental plot.

Rainfall totaled 2,930 mm during 1988 cropping season. EC varied from 2 to

6.5 dS/m and pH, from 3.9 to 4.6. In the screening plot, all but 18 advanced bulk populations from IRRI, 6 elite lines from India, and the local check died. The surviving 25 lines are of long duration and short-statured (see table).

Local variety C-14-8, culture 88-038, and culture 88-121 are found to be promising. □

Agronomic traits related to tolerance for salinity of some promising rice cultures in the marshy swamps of Andamans.^a

Designation	Source	Phenotypic index (0-9)	Days to 50% flowering ^b	Plant height (cm)		Panicle-bearing tillers (no.)		Panicle length (cm)		Seed yield/plant (g)	
				(a)	(r)	(a)	(r)	(a)	(r)	(a)	(r)
88-027	IRRI	6	155	51.0	47.4	6.0	83.3	12.6	54.3	6.0	27.8
88-048	IRRI	9	na	55.5	58.2	3.4	68.0	16.5	68.5	6.8	52.3
88-092	IRRI	5	153	41.8	45.5	7.0	74.5	18.3	72.7	7.0	23.3
88-127	IRRI	3	153	49.0	54.8	6.0	76.9	17.4	83.3	8.4	44.9
88-091	IRRI	4	130	51.6	57.2	4.3	69.4	18.6	78.8	11.2	82.4
88-121	IRRI	4	148	58.8	64.1	5.0	62.5	19.5	95.6	14.0	35.0
88-106	IRRI	4	150	61.4	67.3	3.4	77.3	19.6	86.7	3.4	38.6
88-104	IRRI	7	135	62.2	70.7	3.4	77.3	21.3	99.1	7.5	56.8
88-097	IRRI	7	na	51.4	60.7	3.8	76.0	12.6	64.3	7.6	25.3
88-088	IRRI	7	160	48.0	51.7	3.3	37.5	14.3	74.5	6.9	19.6
88-038	IRRI	5	140	59.5	73.5	5.0	89.3	15.1	83.9	15.0	53.6
88-063	IRRI	4	155	42.3	54.4	4.5	88.9	18.3	80.3	4.0	49.4
88-006	IRRI	5	121	44.7	62.1	3.0	50.0	9.9	57.6	3.0	25.0
88-126	IRRI	5	145	72.0	81.6	4.0	64.5	16.2	70.7	4.4	29.5
88-012	IRRI	6	na	48.9	53.6	4.5	62.5	17.5	81.4	9.0	57.0
88-080	IRRI	6	na	46.3	52.4	4.0	71.4	13.7	59.6	4.0	39.6
88-032	IRRI	3	147	79.0	74.8	6.0	51.7	18.8	88.3	8.4	18.1
88-071	IRRI	9	120	52.5	56.0	3.2	84.2	16.2	69.2	3.2	28.1
SR26-B	India	3	129	95.6	93.3	3.0	83.3	11.6	56.9	3.0	38.0
CO 43	India	5	137	55.8	66.1	4.0	76.9	14.8	67.9	4.0	29.6
CST100-1	India	5	140	52.6	87.1	3.8	95.0	15.4	92.2	5.7	47.5
CSR3	India	5	153	51.8	68.6	2.2	47.8	15.3	86.0	4.0	43.5
316	India	5	138	59.8	68.7	3.5	83.3	14.3	69.8	2.7	29.3
F35	India	5	129	58.5	68.3	5.0	84.0	12.6	68.9	4.2	84.0
C-14-8	India	5	155	142.4	87.4	5.4	58.6	20.6	86.9	11.6	50.4

^a(a) = actual value under saline condition.

(r) = relative value = $\frac{\text{performance under saline condition}}{\text{performance under normal condition}} \times 100$

^bna = not available.

Zhongyu 87-1, promising line developed through shuttle breeding

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Zhongyu 87-1—a high-yielding, medium-duration, multiple-resistance, and wide-adaptability variety developed from the cross Kwangluai 4/IR64 through the IRRI-CNIRRI Shuttle Breeding project—can be grown in middle season or late season. It is resistant to blast and whitebacked planthopper and moderately resistant to bacterial blight and brown planthopper.

In a late season 1988 hybrid rice demonstration test in Zhejiang Province, it yielded higher than Shanyou 6 (hybrid check) in five of six sites (Table 1). In farmers' fields in Zhejiang, it averaged 7.5 t/ha, 7.26% higher than Shanyou 6. In preliminary regional adaptability tests in Hubei Province in middle season 1988, its yield was significantly higher than that of check variety Quichao 2 in three locations (Table 2).

Zhongyu 87-1 has medium height (90-100 cm), compact plant type, and

Table 1. Performance of Zhongyu 87-1 in late season hybrid rice demonstration test.^a Zhejiang, China, 1988.

Location	Height (m)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Sterility (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over Shanyou 6 (%)
Quxian	78.7	9.7	99.3	10.6	29.4	7.1	14.8
Huangyan	81.0	10.3	105.7	13.6	30.8	7.5	5.0
Fuying	83.8	10.4	112.6	12.0	27.8	8.8	42.0
Shuichang	75.1	10.9	91.9	23.1	26.9	5.1	-3.5
Wenlin	-	11.3	116.1	9.7	26.1	8.3	14.3
Leqing	-	12.0	111.6	15.4	27.5	7.4	2.2

^aPlot size = 133 m².

lodging resistance. Panicles are large (106-110 grains/panicle) and grain-filling rate high (85%), with 27-29 g/1,000 grains and 22-23% amylose content. In 1989, Zhongyu 87-1 was promoted to regional adaptability tests in Hubei and Zhejiang. □

Table 2. Yield of Zhongyu 87-1 in midseason rice preliminary regional adaptability tests. Hubei, China, 1988.

Location	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase over Quichao 2 (%)	Rank in test ^b
Wuhan	7.1**	16.5	1
Dongxihu	9.6**	11.6	2
Jinzhou	8.5**	17.3	1

^aOf 11 varieties. ** = significant at P = 0.01.

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Data management and computer modeling

Simulation of yield potential in rice cultivars

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We raised six lowland rice cultivars available from the gene bank of the Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU, Coimbatore, during 1988 wet season and conducted productivity studies. Yield potentials were computer simulated using the MACROS. L1D simulation model developed by IRRI.

Calculated and measured main yield of rice cultivars at Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Cultivar	Calculated grain yield (t/ha)	Measured grain yield (t/ha)	Simulation percentage
ADT36	6.8	6.2	91.2
ADT37	5.1	4.8	94.1
CO 37	7.2	7.0	97.2
ASD16	5.2	5.1	98.1
TKM6	2.3	3.1	134.8
IR66	4.1	5.6	136.6

The program took into account dry matter accumulation, physiological characteristics, and weather prevailing during the growth period.

Observed and calculated grain yield are presented in the table. Measured grain yields within 10% ±100% of calculated grain yield are presented in the figure.

Calculated grain yield and measured yield agree satisfactorily in ADT36, ADT37, CO 37, and ASD16.

This shows that yield potential and production can be reasonably estimated on the basis of cultivar physiological characteristics and growing area weather conditions. □

Calculated and measured grain yield for rice cultivars. Coimbatore, India.

Seed technology

Screening rice varieties for grain dormancy

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Harvest of the second (Feb-Jun) crop at Kuttanad usually coincides with the rainy season. Popular high-yielding varieties grown during the second season lack seed dormancy and considerable loss occurs due to grain sprouting in the field.

We screened germplasm at RRS Moncompu for grain dormancy to